

DETERMINING PARAMETERS IN BLOOD DONATION SIMULATION TO PREDICT THE AVAILABILITY OF BLOOD IN BANDUNG, INDONESIA

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Abstract— Use 10 pt Times font for the body text with one/single line spacing, and 12 pt spacing for the next heading. Left and right indent 0.5cm. Maximum length 200 words.

Keywords: use 10 pt; lower case; italic; Times; write alphabetically in 5-10 words.

I. INTRODUCTION

The current blood stock in Indonesia has not met national needs¹. According to the standard of WHO², a country is estimated to need to maintain a minimum average of 20-25 regular donors per 1000 inhabitants, which means the blood requirement to be self-sufficient in blood supplies is 2%-2.5% of total population. A lot of factors further complicate the situation, such as population growth, shelf life of stored blood, technology to handle the process, etc. More often than not, these factors are not independent of one another; as such, we need a way to simulate and examine how these factors interact in a system.

By using an agent-based model (ABM), a system can be modelled through a bottom-up approach; each agent has its own set of rules it obeys and interacts with other agents. With this, a simple model can be built and a mathematical equation can be derived from it to approximate the output of the model, in this case, the availability of blood. We start from a limited scope (only one city, Bandung, instead of nationwide and taking into account only a few factors), but hopefully, this would become the first step to understanding a complex problem in a bigger scope. Kerangka Teoritis

$$Tahun1 = \sum persediaan\ air - ((20\% \times \sum persediaan\ air) + (\sum dom + \sum nondom))(2)$$

II. BUILDING THE MODEL

In this paper, we will build a model to simulate blood donation using bottom-up approach in NetLogo³, a multi-agent programmable modeling environment. There are two types of agents in the model, people and sites, each having their own sets of rules and properties.

A. Setting Up the Model

As mentioned before, there are two types of agents in the model, people and sites, that behave according to the rules set in the programming. The setup will place them randomly in the world, which has the size of 100 patches * 30 patches.

These are the attributes which are owned by person agents:

1. bloodtype: directly linked to the type of blood a person can donate, as well as the amount of blood needed (2.5% of total population for each bloodtype subset)
2. last-time-donated: a person can only donate after 12-16 weeks⁴ depending on their gender and condition (because the gender and condition are not taken into account here, we default to the average which is 14 weeks)
3. has-donated?: if a person has donated in a span of time, they need to wait until they can donate again
4. regular-donor?: determines whether a person will regularly donate their blood or not, regular donor will always donate their blood if they are able and around a donation site
5. healthy?: determines whether a person will be allowed to donate their blood based on their health, which in the model is limited by the scope of whether they are infected with either HIV, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C, or Syphilis or not, and not taking into account other factors e.g. weight, age.

As for site agents, the attributes are:

1. capacity: how many persons can donate to a certain site in a month
2. a-stock: the stock of A-type blood stored in the site
3. b-stock: the stock of B-type blood stored in the site
4. ab-stock: the stock of AB-type blood stored in the site
5. o-stock: the stock of O-type blood stored in the site

The simulation has 18 control variables, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Parameters of the simulation

The overall interface of the program is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Interface of the simulation

The simulation runs for each discrete step (called 'tick') in which the agents perform their actions. In this model, ten ticks represent one week in real life. People will wander around randomly and donate if there is a donation site nearby and if they are able to. Sites will store the donated blood, and the donated blood will be disposed once it is expired, which is typically six weeks after the donation⁵. Bloodtype distribution

is hardcoded and determined by actual statistics of bloodtype of people of Bandung6.

III. ANALYS

To be able to evaluate the impact of each input variables on the behavior of the simulation, first we determine the 'default' settings using available data and statistics from Disdukcapil Bandung6 (for population-growth), PMI Bandung7 (for % donor and % donor growth) and WHO8 (for disease statistics), as well as assumptions for when actual data is not available. The default settings are the same as the one shown in Figure 1. Then, each of these input variables is tested to evaluate the influence of input parameters on the output indicator, by experimenting them through manipulating the values. The experiment is repeated five times for each variable before they are averaged, to ensure that the data will be representative. In Figure 3, for example, it can be seen what influence the parameter num-of-sites (value 2-10) has on the output indicator, the percentage of blood stock per demand, classified by bloodtypes.

Figure 3 Percentage of blood stock per demand after 12 months (controlled variable: num-of-sites)

From this chart and similar charts for other parameters, it can be seen what parameters have significant influence and how influential they are in relative to others. Parameters with negative R2 are negligible, because the explanation towards response is very low. This leaves us with parameters shown in Table 1-4 for each bloodtype, summarized with the slope of regression line for each parameter that influences the output indicator. The higher the slope value is, the more influence it has.

Table 1

Slope of regression line for each input parameter (Type A)

No	Parameter	Slope of regression line
1	num-of-sites	31.93
2	site-effectiveness	33.23
3	%-a-donor	28.64
4	%-a-donor-growth	22.73

Table 2

Slope of regression line for each input parameter (Type B)

No	Parameter	Slope of regression line
1	num-of-sites	56.61
2	site-effectiveness	40.37
3	%-b-donor	30.50
4	%-b-donor-growth	29.03

Table 3

Slope of regression line for each input parameter (Type AB)

No	Parameter	Slope of regression line
1	num-of-sites	60.40
2	site-effectiveness	71.64
3	%-ab-donor	39.44
4	%-ab-donor-growth	17.80

Table 4

Slope of regression line for each input parameter (Type O)

No	Parameter	Slope of regression line
1	num-of-sites	34.35
2	site-effectiveness	34.44
3	%-o-donor	18.90
4	%-o-donor-growth	15.03

By sorting the parameters, we can determine the three parameters with biggest influence to derive the mathematical equation through multivariate regression9. The process is indicated in Tables 5-8 for A, B, AB, and O respectively.

Table 5

Multivariate regression results (Type A) (R2 = 0.997)

No	Parameter	Coefficient
1	num-of-sites	23.14
2	site-effectiveness	-13.83
3	%-a-donor	38.40
4	Intercept	-145.82

Table 6

Multivariate regression results (Type B) (R2 = 0.888)

No	Parameter	Coefficient
1	num-of-sites	33.71
2	site-effectiveness	176.16
3	%-b-donor	34.92
4	Intercept	-255.23

Table 7

Multivariate regression results (Type AB) (R2 = 0.967)

No	Parameter	Coefficient
1	num-of-sites	68.20
2	site-effectiveness	-85.70
3	%-ab-donor	123.08
4	Intercept	-496.51

Table 8
Multivariate regression results (Type O) (R2 = 0.998)

No	Parameter	Coefficient
1	num-of-sites	24.27
2	site-effectiveness	2.15
3	%-o-donor	41.05
4	Intercept	-163.126

The R2 tells us that these parameters have given us approximately 99.7%, 88.8%, 96.7%, and 99.8% of the information and explained the variations of our model by these percentages for A, B, AB, and O respectively.

As for approximating blood availability in the future, we can derive a simple mathematical model to predict blood availability relative to the needs, by deriving equation from trendline of the blood availability (Figure 4-7).

Figure 4 A-type blood availability (with equation on chart)

Figure 5 B-type blood availability (with equation on chart)

Figure 6 AB-type blood availability (with equation on chart)

Figure 7 O-type blood availability (with equation on chart)

IV. CONCLUSION

- A-type and O-type blood availability does not meet nationwide requirements of 2.5% of total population with the same bloodtype in two years time.
- Within time, the requirements for B-type and AB-type are met.
- Population, capacity, and diseases have negligible influences on the output indicator in the model. Population is scalable, capacity never gets full in a month, and % of people who are infected with diseases are too few to have actual effect.
- Further study and modification: are there any forgotten factors playing a role? Model is still too simple – it doesn't take into account the different kinds of blood (whole blood, plasma, etc), age, weight, whether the potential donors have health problems that prevent them to donate for the time being, schedule, layout of the world, etc.

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